

Extending the Range of Temporal Specifications of the Run-Time Event Calculus

Periklis Mantenoglou

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece
NCSR “Demokritos”, Greece

Alexander Artikis

University of Piraeus, Greece
NCSR “Demokritos”, Greece

Abstract

Composite event recognition (CER) frameworks reason over streams of low-level, symbolic events in order to detect instances of spatio-temporal patterns defining high-level, composite activities. The Event Calculus is a temporal, logical formalism that has been used to define composite activities in CER, while RTEC_o is a formal CER framework that detects composite activities based on their Event Calculus definitions. RTEC_o , however, cannot handle every possible set of Event Calculus definitions for composite activities, limiting the range of CER applications supported by RTEC_o . We propose RTEC_β , an extension of RTEC_o that supports arbitrary composite activity specifications in the Event Calculus. We present the syntax, semantics, reasoning algorithms and time complexity of RTEC_β . Our analysis demonstrates that RTEC_β extends the scope of RTEC_o , supporting every possible set of Event Calculus definitions for composite activities, while maintaining the high reasoning efficiency of RTEC_o .

2012 ACM Subject Classification Computing methodologies → Temporal reasoning

Keywords and phrases Event Calculus, temporal pattern matching, composite event recognition

Digital Object Identifier 10.4230/LIPIcs.TIME.2024.3

Supplementary Material *Software*: <https://github.com/aartikis/rtec>

Funding This work was supported by the EU-funded CREXDATA project (No 101092749), and partly supported by the University of Piraeus Research Center.

1 Introduction

Composite event recognition (CER) involves the detection of composite activities by reasoning over streams of time-stamped, symbolic events [16, 20]. A CER framework employs an activity specification language, where it is possible to express the spatio-temporal combinations of input events that form each activity of interest in some application domain. In human activity recognition, e.g., we may specify the time periods during which two people are ‘gathering’ using a pattern stating that at least one of the two people is walking towards the other one, while, at the same time, the distance between them is a few meters and they are facing each other. As another example, in the task of monitoring composite maritime activities, we may define ‘trawling’, i.e., a type of fishing activity that involves several consecutive turns, as a sequence of ‘change in heading’ events.

The literature contains numerous CER frameworks [1, 20], several of which are automata-based [32, 39, 21]. CORE, e.g., is a formal automata-based CER system that has proven to be more efficient than other contemporary automata-based engines [10]. CORE is restricted to unary relations, while the composite activities derived by CORE cannot be used as building blocks in other patterns. In other words, CORE does not support relational and hierarchical composite activity specifications. There are also logic-based CER formalisms [17, 11, 8]. For

© Periklis Mantenoglou and Alexander Artikis;
licensed under Creative Commons License CC-BY 4.0

31st International Symposium on Temporal Representation and Reasoning (TIME 2024).

Editors: Pietro Sala, Michael Sioutis, and Fusheng Wang; Article No. 3; pp. 3:1–3:14

Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics

LIPICs Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, Dagstuhl Publishing, Germany

instance, there are several frameworks supporting fragments of the LARS language [5] that are suitable for CER [6, 4, 18]. MeTeoR is a logic-based CER engine whose language extends DatalogMTL with windowing [37, 38]. The Chronicle Recognition System (CRS) represents composite activities as sets of events that are associated with time constraints [17]. The language of CRS includes several operators, such as sequencing, iteration and negation. These formalisms support relational composite activities, as well as compositional specifications, paving the way for hierarchical definitions. Moreover, logic-based formalisms typically exhibit a formal and declarative semantics, as opposed to automata-based approaches, which do not always come with a clear semantics, making them hard to evaluate and generalise [21].

The Event Calculus is a logic programming formalism for representing and reasoning about events and their effects over time [24]. The Event Calculus may be used as an activity specification language for CER, as it exhibits a formal, declarative semantics, while supporting relational and hierarchical activity specifications that may include background knowledge [27, 20]. Moreover, the Event Calculus includes a built-in representation of inertia, allowing for succinct composite activity patterns, and thus code maintenance. The Event Calculus has been employed in various settings, including mobility assistance [9], reactive and proactive health monitoring [13, 22] and simulations with cognitive agents [34]. The ‘Macro Event Calculus’, e.g., uses ‘macro-events’ to support composite event operators, such as sequence, disjunction, parallelism and iteration [12]. The ‘Interval-based Event Calculus’ incorporates durative events and supports sequencing, concurrency and negation [28]. jREC is a reactive implementation of the Cached Event Calculus [14] which is optimised for CER [7, 19]. The Run-Time Event Calculus (RTEC) extends the Event Calculus with optimisation techniques for CER, such as windowing, indexing and caching [3]. In order to perform CER with minimal latency, RTEC processes hierarchies of composite activity definitions bottom-up, while caching and reusing the derived instances of composite activities, thus avoiding re-computations. RTEC has proven highly efficient in demanding CER applications, including city transport management [3], maritime situational awareness [30] and commercial fleet management [36], outperforming the state-of-the-art [26, 25, 36].

RTEC does not support every possible composite activity definition that may be expressed in the Event Calculus. In human activity recognition, e.g., there is a need to model composite activities defined in terms of the concept ‘ $movement(P_1, P_2)$ ’, expressing the relative movement between persons P_1 and P_2 . For instance, ‘ $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$ ’ expresses that P_1 and P_2 are moving towards one another in order to have a meeting, and ‘ $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ ’ denotes that, while P_1 and P_2 are talking to each other, one of them is moving his arms abruptly. Furthermore, it may be desirable to express that P_1 and P_2 may be making abrupt gestures to each other only after they have gathered close to one another, i.e., $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ depends on $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$. RTEC does not support Event Calculus definitions where composite activities characterised by the same underlying concept, such as $movement(P_1, P_2)$, depend on each other. To address this issue, we propose an extension of RTEC that supports an arbitrary set of Event Calculus definitions.

Our starting point is RTEC_o, an extension of RTEC that supports Event Calculus definitions with cyclic dependencies, which are often required for CER [26], and propose RTEC_{fl}, an extension of RTEC_o that supports every possible set of composite activity definitions in the Event Calculus. Our contributions are the following. First, we present the semantics of RTEC_{fl}. Second, we present a compiler for RTEC_{fl}, identifying the reasoning algorithm that needs to be used at run-time in order to resolve each condition of a composite activity definition. Third, we outline the time complexity of RTEC_{fl}, demonstrating that

92 its cost is the same as RTEC_\circ , while supporting a wider range of temporal specifications.
 93 RTEC_β and its compiler are publicly available¹.

94 2 Background

95 Our starting point is RTEC_\circ , i.e., a recent extension of the Run-Time Event Calculus (RTEC)
 96 that supports efficient reasoning over temporal specifications with cyclic dependencies [26]
 97 (the other extensions of RTEC are orthogonal to this work). We present the syntax, semantics
 98 and reasoning algorithms of RTEC_\circ . In Section 3, we outline the limitations of RTEC_\circ , and,
 99 in Section 4, we present an extension of RTEC_\circ that supports every set of Event Calculus
 100 definitions.

101 2.1 Syntax & Semantics

102 The language of RTEC_\circ follows the Event Calculus, which is many-sorted, including sorts
 103 for representing time, instantaneous events and ‘fluents’, i.e., properties that may have
 104 different values at different points in time. The time model comprises a linear time-line with
 105 non-negative integer time-points. $\text{happensAt}(E, T)$ signifies that event E occurs at time-point
 106 T . $\text{initiatedAt}(F = V, T)$ (resp. $\text{terminatedAt}(F = V, T)$) expresses that a time period during
 107 which a fluent F has the value V continuously is initiated (terminated) at time-point T .
 108 $\text{holdsAt}(F = V, T)$ states that F has value V at T , while $\text{holdsFor}(F = V, I)$ expresses that the
 109 ‘fluent-value pair’ (FVP) $F = V$ holds continuously in the maximal intervals included in list I .

110 In CER, happensAt is used to express the input events of the stream, while FVPs express
 111 composite activities. A formalisation of the activity specification of a domain in the Event
 112 Calculus is called *event description*.

113 ► **Definition 1** (Event Description). *An event description \mathcal{E} is a set of:*
 114 ■ *ground $\text{happensAt}(E, T)$ facts, expressing a stream of event instances, and*
 115 ■ *rules with head $\text{initiatedAt}(F = V, T)$ or $\text{terminatedAt}(F = V, T)$, expressing the effects of*
 116 *events on FVP $F = V$. ■*

117 ► **Definition 2** (Syntax of the Rules in the Event Description). *$\text{initiatedAt}(F = V, T)$ rules have*
 118 *the following syntax:*

$$119 \quad \text{initiatedAt}(F = V, T) \leftarrow \begin{array}{l} \text{happensAt}(E_1, T) [[[\text{not}] \text{happensAt}(E_2, T), \dots, [\text{not}] \text{happensAt}(E_n, T), \\ [\text{not}] \text{holdsAt}(F_1 = V_1, T), \dots, [\text{not}] \text{holdsAt}(F_k = V_k, T)]] \end{array} \quad (1)$$

120 *The first body literal of an initiatedAt rule is a positive happensAt predicate; this is followed by a*
 121 *possibly empty set, denoted by ‘[[]]’, of positive/negative happensAt and holdsAt predicates. ‘not’*
 122 *expresses negation-by-failure [15], while ‘[not]’ denotes that ‘not’ is optional. All (head and*
 123 *body) predicates are evaluated on the same time-point T . The bodies of $\text{terminatedAt}(F = V, T)$*
 124 *rules have the same form. ■*

125 ► **Example 3** (Event Description for Human Activity Recognition). In human activity recog-
 126 nition, we apply rules on streams containing symbolic representations of video feeds [2].
 127 In general, such rules are constructed in collaboration with domain experts or learned
 128 from data [23]. We use the fluent $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2)$ to express that people P_1 and P_2

¹ <https://github.com/aartikis/RTEC>

3:4 Extending the Range of Temporal Specifications of the Run-Time Event Calculus

129 are interacting, while the value of $interaction(P_1, P_2)$ denotes the stage of the interac-
 130 tion. The ‘greeting’ stage of $interaction(P_1, P_2)$ denotes that P_1 and P_2 are greeting each
 131 other at a distance. Below, we outline a set of rules included in the specification of FVP
 132 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &initiatedAt(interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(active(P_1), T), happensAt(active(P_2), T), \\
 &\quad holdsAt(distance(P_1, P_2) = mid, T), holdsAt(orientation(P_1, P_2) = facing, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &terminatedAt(interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(walking(P_1), T), \\
 &\quad not\ holdsAt(orientation(P_1, P_2) = facing, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &terminatedAt(interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(walking(P_2), T), \\
 &\quad not\ holdsAt(orientation(P_1, P_2) = facing, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

136 According to rule (2), P_1 and P_2 start greeting when both of them are ‘active’, i.e., moving
 137 their arms while in the same position, the distance between them is a few meters, denoted
 138 by the value ‘mid’, and they are facing towards one another. Rules (3)–(4) express that P_1
 139 and P_2 stop greeting when one of them starts walking, while they are not facing each other.
 140 The FVPs $distance(P_1, P_2) = mid$ and $orientation(P_1, P_2) = facing$ are defined based on
 141 the coordinates and the orientation of the tracked people, which are provided in the input
 142 stream.

143 Moreover, we may use the fluent $movement(P_1, P_2)$ to express the relative movement
 144 between people P_1 and P_2 and the value ‘gathering’ of $movement(P_1, P_2)$ to denote that P_1
 145 and P_2 are approaching one another. The specification of FVP $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$
 146 includes the following rules:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &initiatedAt(movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(walking(P_1), T), \\
 &\quad holdsAt(distance(P_1, P_2) = mid, T), holdsAt(orientation(P_1, P_2) = facing, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &initiatedAt(movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(walking(P_2), T), \\
 &\quad holdsAt(distance(P_1, P_2) = mid, T), holdsAt(orientation(P_1, P_2) = facing, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &terminatedAt(movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(active(P_1), T), not\ happensAt(walking(P_2), T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &terminatedAt(movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering, T) \leftarrow \\
 &\quad happensAt(active(P_2), T), not\ happensAt(walking(P_1), T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

151 Rules (5)–(6) state that P_1 and P_2 start gathering when one of them is walking towards
 152 the other person, while their distance is a few meters and they are facing each other. Rules
 153 (7)–(8) express that P_1 and P_2 stop gathering when one of them is being active, while the
 154 other person is not walking. \diamond

155 The dependencies among the FVPs in an event description can be expressed in the form
 156 of a *dependency graph*.

157 **► Definition 4 (Dependency Graph).** *The dependency graph of an event description is a*
 158 *directed graph $G = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where:*

- 159 1. \mathcal{V} contains one vertex $v_F = V$ for each FVP $F = V$.

(a) The dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_1}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_1 (continuous lines), the dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_2 (continuous and dashed lines), and the dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_3 (all lines). For simplicity, a vertex v_j is displayed as j .

(b) The fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ of \mathcal{E}_2 . The contracted fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{cdfl}$ of \mathcal{E}_2 is the same as $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$.

(c) The fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{fl}$ of \mathcal{E}_3 .

(d) The contracted fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{cdfl}$ of \mathcal{E}_3 . We display a vertex v_{S_i} of a contracted fluent dependency graph, where S_i is a SCC of the corresponding fluent dependency graph, as the set of fluents whose vertices are in S_i .

■ **Figure 1** Dependency graphs, fluent dependency graphs and contracted fluent dependency graphs. We use distinct shapes for the vertices of each type of graph to aid the presentation.

160 2. \mathcal{E} contains an edge $(v_{F_j} = V_j, v_{F_i} = V_i)$ iff there is an *initiatedAt* or *terminatedAt* rule for $F_i = V_i$
 161 having *holdsAt* $(F_j = V_j, T)$ as one of its conditions. ■

162 The vertices and edges of Figure 1a that are drawn with continuous lines, e.g., comprise
 163 the dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_1}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_1 , which contains rules (2)–(8) of Example
 164 3.

165 Based on the dependency graph of an event description, it is possible to define a function
 166 *level* that maps the FVPs of the event description to the positive integers. Towards defining
 167 an FVP level function, we define the *level of a vertex* in a directed acyclic graph as follows:

168 ► **Definition 5** (Vertex Level). *Given a directed acyclic graph, the level of a vertex v is equal*
 169 *to:*

- 170 1. 1, if v has no incoming edges.
- 171 2. n , where $n > 1$, if v has at least one incoming edge from a vertex of level $n-1$, and zero
 172 or more incoming edges from vertices of levels lower than $n-1$. ■

173 A dependency graph may or may not be acyclic. Given an acyclic dependency graph, the
 174 level of an FVP $F=V$ is defined as the level of vertex $v_{F=V}$ in the dependency graph. In the
 175 acyclic dependency graph of Figure 1a, e.g., $v_{interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting}$ has level 2, and thus
 176 FVP $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$ has level 2. In order to handle cyclic dependency graphs,
 177 we employ the *contracted dependency graph* of an event description, which is, by definition,
 178 acyclic. Then, we define the *level of an FVP* based on the level of the corresponding vertex
 179 in the contracted dependency graph.

180 A directed graph becomes acyclic by contracting its strongly connected components
181 (SCC)s into single vertices.

182 ► **Definition 6** (SCC Contracted Graph). *Given a directed graph $G=(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ and the SCCs*
183 *S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n of G , the SCC contracted graph $G^{cd}=(\mathcal{V}^{cd}, \mathcal{E}^{cd})$ of G is defined as follows:*

- 184 1. $\mathcal{V}^{cd} = \bigcup_{1 \leq i \leq n} \{v_{S_i}\}$.
- 185 2. $(v_{S_i}, v_{S_j}) \in \mathcal{E}^{cd}$ iff $\exists v_i, v_j \in \mathcal{V}$, such that $v_i \in S_i, v_j \in S_j, S_i \neq S_j$ and $(v_i, v_j) \in \mathcal{E}$. ■

186 ► **Definition 7** (Contracted Dependency Graph). *Consider an event description with de-*
187 *pendency graph G . The contracted dependency graph of the event description is the SCC*
188 *contracted graph of G . ■*

189 The dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_i}$ in Figure 1a is acyclic, i.e., every SCCs of $G_{\mathcal{E}_i}$ contains one
190 vertex. As a result, the contracted dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{cd}$ of $G_{\mathcal{E}_i}$ is the same as $G_{\mathcal{E}_i}$.

191 ► **Definition 8** (FVP Level in RTEC_o). *Consider an event description with dependency graph*
192 *G and contracted dependency graph G^{cd} . The level of an FVP $F=V$, such that vertex $v_{F=V}$*
193 *is included in SCC S_i of G , is equal to the level of vertex v_{S_i} in G^{cd} . ■*

194 RTEC_o supports event descriptions where FVPs with the same fluent have the same
195 FVP level. For such an event description, a local stratification may be constructed as follows.
196 The first stratum contains all groundings of `happensAt`. The remaining strata are formed by
197 following, in a bottom-up fashion, the levels of FVPs. For each FVP level l without cyclic
198 dependencies, we have one stratum containing the ground predicates for FVPs with level l .
199 For each FVP level l with cyclic dependencies, the ground predicates for FVPs with level
200 l have to be stratified further in terms of their time-stamp. We introduce an additional
201 stratum for each time-point of the window, i.e., the finite portion of the stream currently
202 being processing by RTEC_o.

203 ► **Proposition 9** (Semantics of RTEC_o). *Consider an event description \mathcal{E} where the FVPs*
204 *with the same fluent have the same FVP level (see Definition 8). \mathcal{E} is a locally stratified logic*
205 *program [33]. ◆*

206 2.2 Reasoning & Complexity

207 The key reasoning task of RTEC_o is the computation of `holdsFor($F=V, I$)`, i.e., the list of
208 maximal intervals I during which each FVP $F=V$ of the event description holds continuously.
209 Recall that, in CER, FVPs express the composite activities that we are interested in detecting.
210 RTEC_o computes list I in `holdsFor($F=V, I$)` as follows. First, it computes the initiations of
211 $F=V$ based on the rules of the event description with head `initiatedAt($F=V, T$)`. Second,
212 if there is at least one initiation of $F=V$, then RTEC_o computes the terminations of
213 $F=V$ based on the rules with head `terminatedAt($F=V, T$)`, as well as the rules with head
214 `initiatedAt($F=V', T$)`, where $V' \neq V$. Third, RTEC_o computes the maximal intervals of
215 $F=V$ by matching each initiation T_s of $F=V$ with the first termination T_e of $F=V$ after
216 T_s , ignoring every intermediate initiation between T_s and T_e . `holdsAt($F=V, T$)` may then
217 be evaluated by checking whether T belongs to one of the maximal intervals of FVP $F=V$.

218 RTEC_o processes FVPs in a bottom-up manner, computing and caching their intervals
219 level-by-level. In order to derive the initiations and the terminations of an FVP $F=V$, we eval-
220 uate the `initiatedAt` and `terminatedAt` rules defining $F=V$. The body of such a rule may include
221 a `holdsAt($F'=V', T$)` condition (see rule schema (1)), leading to an edge $(v_{F'=V'}, v_{F=V})$
222 in the dependency graph (see Definition 4). We distinguish two cases for the evaluation of
223 `holdsAt($F'=V', T$)`:

- 224 1. Vertices $v_{F'=V'}$ and $v_{F=V}$ are not part of a cycle in the dependency graph. In this
 225 case, $v_{F'=V'}$ and $v_{F=V}$ are in different SCCs of the dependency graph and, based on
 226 edge $(v_{F'=V'}, v_{F=V})$, $F'=V'$ has a lower level than $F=V$ (see Definition 8). Since
 227 RTEC_o processes FVPs in ascending FVP level order, at the time of processing $F=V$, the
 228 intervals of $F'=V'$ that are required to compute $\text{holdsAt}(F'=V', T)$ have been derived
 229 and cached at a previous step. As a result, $\text{holdsAt}(F'=V', T)$ is resolved by fetching
 230 the intervals of $F'=V'$ from the cache and checking whether T belongs to one of those
 231 intervals, without the need for re-computation.
- 232 2. Vertices $v_{F'=V'}$ and $v_{F=V}$ are part of a cycle in the dependency graph. In this case,
 233 $v_{F'=V'}$ and $v_{F=V}$ are in the same SCC of the dependency graph, and thus $F'=V'$ and
 234 $F=V$ have the same level (see Definition 8). As a result, RTEC_o may process $F=V$
 235 before $F'=V'$, in which case the intervals of $F'=V'$ are not be present in the cache at
 236 the time of processing $F=V$. To address this issue, RTEC_o computes $\text{holdsAt}(F'=V', T)$
 237 using the incremental caching techniques presented in [26].

238 3 Problem Statement

239 Towards a more accurate domain specification for human activity recognition, we may extend
 240 event description \mathcal{E}_1 of Example 3 with a definition for an FVP expressing that two people
 241 are talking.

242 ► **Example 10** (Representing $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{talking}$ (Example 3 cont'd)). After having
 243 approached one another, persons P_1 and P_2 may start talking, in which case the value of
 244 the $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2)$ fluent should change from ‘greeting’ to ‘talking’. The specification of
 245 FVP $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{talking}$ includes the following rules:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{initiatedAt}(\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{talking}, T) \leftarrow \\
 & \quad \text{happensAt}(\text{active}(P_1), T), \\
 & \quad \text{holdsAt}(\text{distance}(P_1, P_2) = \text{short}, T), \text{holdsAt}(\text{orientation}(P_1, P_2) = \text{facing}, T), \\
 & \quad \text{not holdsAt}(\text{movement}(P_1, P_2) = \text{gathering}, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{initiatedAt}(\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{talking}, T) \leftarrow \\
 & \quad \text{happensAt}(\text{active}(P_2), T), \\
 & \quad \text{holdsAt}(\text{distance}(P_1, P_2) = \text{short}, T), \text{holdsAt}(\text{orientation}(P_1, P_2) = \text{facing}, T), \\
 & \quad \text{not holdsAt}(\text{movement}(P_1, P_2) = \text{gathering}, T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{terminatedAt}(\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{talking}, T) \leftarrow \\
 & \quad \text{happensAt}(\text{inactive}(P_1), T), \text{happensAt}(\text{inactive}(P_2), T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

249 According to rules (9)–(10), P_1 and P_2 start talking when one of them is being active, while
 250 their distance is about one meter, denoted by ‘short’, they are facing one another and their
 251 relative movement is not ‘gathering’, i.e., P_1 and P_2 are not moving towards one another.
 252 Rule (11) denotes that P_1 and P_2 stop talking when neither of them is being active. \diamond

253 A fluent cannot have more than one value at any time; an initiation of an FVP $F = V_1$ implies
 254 a termination of FVP $F = V_2$, where $V_1 \neq V_2$. As a result, there are implicit dependencies
 255 among FVPs with the same fluent. For instance, in the event description of Example 10,
 256 FVPs $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{greeting}$ and $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{talking}$ implicitly depend on
 257 each other.

258 The vertices and edges of Figure 1a that are drawn with continuous or dashed lines
 259 comprise the dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_2 , i.e., the extension of event
 260 description \mathcal{E}_1 with rules (9)–(11) of Example 10. FVPs $\text{interaction}(P_1, P_2) = \text{greeting}$ and

261 $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$ have level 2, while FVP $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ has
 262 level 3 (see Definition 8).

263 Event description \mathcal{E}_2 contains FVPs with the same fluent and different levels, which is com-
 264 mon in CER specifications. In city transport management, e.g., fluent ‘ $punctuality(Vh)$ ’ may
 265 be used to monitor the punctuality level of a vehicle Vh over time [3]. $punctuality(Vh) = low$
 266 may be initiated when Vh leaves a stop earlier than scheduled while $punctuality(Vh) = mid$
 267 holds. As another example, in maritime activity monitoring, we may employ the fluent
 268 ‘ $fishing_trip(Vl)$ ’ to survey a fishing trip of a vessel Vl [30]. FVP $fishing_trip(Vl) = ended$ may
 269 depend on FVP $fishing_trip(Vl) = returning$, which expresses the previous stage of the trip.
 270 In these cases, FVP $punctuality(Vh) = low$ has a higher level than FVP $punctuality = mid$,
 271 and FVP $fishing_trip(Vl) = ended$ has a higher level than FVP $fishing_trip(Vl) = returning$
 272 (see Definition 8).

273 RTEC_o does not support event descriptions, such as \mathcal{E}_2 , where FVPs with the same
 274 fluent have different levels. Suppose that FVP $F = V_1$ has level n and FVP $F = V_2$ has level
 275 m , where $n < m$, and that RTEC_o is currently processing the FVPs with level n . When
 276 processing $F = V_1$, RTEC_o needs to evaluate the rules with head $initiatedAt(F = V_2, T)$, as
 277 the initiation of $F = V_2$ constitute terminations of $F = V_1$. Such a rule may include a body
 278 condition referring to an FVP $F' = V'$ with level n' , where $n \leq n' < m$. Since $F' = V'$ has a
 279 lower level than $F = V_2$, RTEC_o attempts to evaluate $holdsAt(F' = V', T)$ by retrieving the
 280 intervals of $F' = V'$ from the cache, in order to check whether T belongs to one of them.
 281 However, the cache of RTEC_o may not contain the intervals of $F' = V'$ at this time, because
 282 $F' = V'$ has level n' and RTEC_o is currently processing the FVPs with level n , where $n \leq n'$,
 283 compromising correctness.

284 In the case of event description \mathcal{E}_2 , when processing $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$,
 285 RTEC_o evaluates the initiations of $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$, as they are terminations of
 286 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$. According to rules (9)–(10) of event description \mathcal{E}_2 , the initi-
 287 ations of $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ depend on FVP $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$, whose
 288 intervals may not present in the cache at the time of processing $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$.
 289 For this reason, RTEC_o does not support event description \mathcal{E}_2 .

290 One way to address this issue is to assign to FVP $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$ a higher
 291 level than the level of FVP $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$. According to dependency graph
 292 $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}$ (see Figure 1a), since there is no FVP that depends on FVP $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$,
 293 we may increase the level of $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$ to 3 without producing an FVP
 294 level assignment that compromises the correctness of the bottom-up processing of RTEC_o. In
 295 this way, $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$ is processed before $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$,
 296 and thus, at the time of processing $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$, the maximal intervals of
 297 $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$ are present in the cache of RTEC_o, avoiding the aforemen-
 298 tioned error.

299 However, it is not always possible to circumvent the issues introduced by FVPs with the
 300 same fluent and different levels by increasing the level of an FVP. Consider the following
 301 example, where we extend event description \mathcal{E}_2 with a definition for an FVP expressing that
 302 two people are making abrupt movements while talking.

303 ► **Example 11** (Representing $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ (Example 10 cont'd)).
 304 While people P_1 and P_2 are talking, they may start moving their arms abruptly, possibly
 305 indicating that a fight between P_1 and P_2 is about to start. The specification of FVP

306 $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ includes the following rules:

$$307 \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{initiatedAt}(movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures, T) \leftarrow \\ & \text{happensAt}(abrupt(P_1), T), \\ & \text{holdsAt}(interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking, T). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$308 \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{initiatedAt}(movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures, T) \leftarrow \\ & \text{happensAt}(abrupt(P_2), T), \\ & \text{holdsAt}(interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking, T). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$309 \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{terminatedAt}(movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures, T) \leftarrow \\ & \text{happensAt}(active(P_1), T), \text{ not happensAt}(abrupt(P_2), T). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$310 \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{terminatedAt}(movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures, T) \leftarrow \\ & \text{happensAt}(active(P_2), T), \text{ not happensAt}(abrupt(P_1), T). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

311 Rules (12)–(13) denote that $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ is initiated when one of
 312 the people P_1 and P_2 starts moving abruptly while the two of them are talking. Rules
 313 (14)–(15) express that we have a termination of $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ when
 314 one of the two people starts being active while the other one is not moving abruptly. \diamond

315 All the vertices and edges in Figure 1a compose dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}$ of event description
 316 \mathcal{E}_3 , i.e., the extension of event description \mathcal{E}_2 with rules (12)–(15). According to dependency
 317 graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}$, FVP $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ has level 4.

318 Event description \mathcal{E}_3 contains FVPs with the same fluent and different levels. The FVPs
 319 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$ and $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ have level 2 and 3, respec-
 320 tively, while FVPs $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$ and $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$
 321 have level 2 and 4. As a result, RTEC_o does not support event description \mathcal{E}_3 . When
 322 processing FVP $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$, RTEC_o may need to evaluate its termina-
 323 tions, which include the initiations of FVP $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$. Accord-
 324 ing to rules (12)–(13), the initiations of $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ depend on
 325 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$, whose intervals are not present in the cache at this time.

326 In this case, it is not possible to set the level of $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$ to 4, with
 327 the goal of processing $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ before $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$, be-
 328 cause there is an edge $(v_{movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering}, v_{interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking})$ in $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}$, implying
 329 that we cannot process $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ before $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$.
 330 These FVPs should have the same level. Moreover, $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$ depends on
 331 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$, and vice versa, which means that these FVPs should also have
 332 the same level. Therefore, $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$, $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$,
 333 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ and $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ should have the same
 334 level, i.e., 2, implying that these FVPs must be processed with incremental caching (see the
 335 second case presented in Section 2.2).

336 **4 Proposed Solution**

337 We propose RTEC_{fl}, an extension of RTEC_o that supports event descriptions where the
 338 vertices of FVPs with the same fluent may have different levels, such as event descriptions \mathcal{E}_2
 339 and \mathcal{E}_3 . To achieve this, RTEC_{fl} incorporates a new definition for FVP level that takes into
 340 account the implicit dependencies between FVPs with the same fluent. We demonstrate that,
 341 based on the definition of FVP level in RTEC_{fl}, we may construct a local stratification for
 342 every possible event description. Afterwards, we propose a compiler for RTEC_{fl}, identifying
 343 the $\text{holdsAt}(F = V, T)$ conditions that need to be resolved with the incremental caching

344 technique proposed in [26], because the intervals of $F=V$ may not be present in the cache
 345 at the time of evaluating $\text{holdsAt}(F=V, T)$. We outline the cost of RTEC_{fl} , showing that
 346 it is the same as the cost of RTEC_o . Therefore, RTEC_{fl} extends the range of temporal
 347 specifications supported by RTEC_o , while maintaining its high reasoning efficiency.

348 4.1 Syntax & Semantics

349 In RTEC_{fl} , all FVPs with the same fluent have the same level. This is achieved by determining
 350 FVP level based on the *fluent dependency graph* of the event description, which is defined as
 351 follows:

352 ► **Definition 12** (Fluent Dependency Graph). *Consider an event description with dependency*
 353 *graph $G=(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$. The fluent dependency graph of the event description is a directed graph*
 354 *$G^{fl}=(\mathcal{V}^{fl}, \mathcal{E}^{fl})$, where:*

- 355 1. \mathcal{V}^{fl} contains one vertex v_F for each fluent F .
- 356 2. \mathcal{E}^{fl} contains an edge (v_{F_1}, v_{F_2}) , where $F_1 \neq F_2$, iff there is an edge $(v_{F_1=V_1}, v_{F_2=V_2})$ in
 357 \mathcal{E} , where V_1 and V_2 are values of fluents F_1 and F_2 , respectively. ■

358 Figure 1b, e.g., depicts the fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_2 of Example
 359 10. Vertex $v_{interaction(P_1, P_2)}$ of $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ corresponds to vertices $v_{interaction(P_1, P_2)=greeting}$ and
 360 $v_{interaction(P_1, P_2)=talking}$ of $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}$, inheriting their incoming edges.

361 The fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ is acyclic. Therefore, we may assign to each FVP $F=V$
 362 of event description \mathcal{E}_2 the level of vertex v_F in the fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$, which is
 363 derived by following Definition 5. It could be the case, however, that the fluent dependency
 364 graph of an event description contains cycles. Figure 1c, e.g., depicts the fluent dependency
 365 graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{fl}$ of event description \mathcal{E}_3 . $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{fl}$ includes a cycle, while, according to Definition 5,
 366 the level of a vertex is defined only on acyclic graphs. To address this issue, we contract the
 367 vertices of the fluent dependency graph that are in the same strongly connected component
 368 (SCC), leading to an acyclic graph. We define the *contracted fluent dependency graph* as
 369 follows:

370 ► **Definition 13** (Contracted Fluent Dependency Graph). *Consider an event description with*
 371 *fluent dependency graph G^{fl} . The contracted fluent dependency graph G^{cdf} of the event*
 372 *description is the SCC contracted graph of G^{fl} . ■*

373 Consider, e.g., the fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ of Figure 1b. $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ is acyclic, and thus every
 374 SCC of $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ contains one vertex. As a result, the contracted fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{cdf}$
 375 of $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$ is the same as $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{fl}$. As another example, Figure 1d presents the contracted fluent
 376 dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{cdf}$ corresponding to the fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{fl}$ in Figure 1c,
 377 which is produced by contracting vertices $v_{movement(P_1, P_2)}$ and $v_{interaction(P_1, P_2)}$ of $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{fl}$, as
 378 these vertices are in the same SCC of $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{fl}$. Due to this contraction of vertices, $G_{\mathcal{E}_3}^{cdf}$ is
 379 acyclic.

380 We may assign a level to each vertex in a contracted fluent dependency graph by following
 381 Definition 5. We define the *level of an FVP* in RTEC_{fl} as follows:

382 ► **Definition 14** (FVP Level in RTEC_{fl}). *Consider an event description with fluent dependency*
 383 *graph G^{fl} and contracted fluent dependency graph G^{cdf} . The level of an FVP $F=V$, such*
 384 *that vertex v_F is included in SCC S_i of G^{fl} , is equal to the level of vertex vs_i of G^{cdf} . ■*

385 Based on Definition 14, FVPs with the same fluent have the same level. In the case of
 386 event description \mathcal{E}_2 , e.g., where the contracted fluent dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{cdf}$ of \mathcal{E}_2 matches

Algorithm 1 *compile*(\mathcal{E})

```

1:  $G_{\mathcal{E}}^{cdf}$   $\leftarrow$  construct_contracted_fluent_dependency_graph( $\mathcal{E}$ )
2: level  $\leftarrow$  compute_fvp_level( $G_{\mathcal{E}}^{cdf}$ )
3: for each rule  $r$  in  $\mathcal{E}$  do
4:    $F = V \leftarrow$  get_fvp_in_head( $r$ )
5:   for each condition ‘[not] holdsAt( $F' = V', T$ )’ in the body of  $r$  do  $\triangleright$  not is optional.
6:     if level[ $F' = V'$ ] = level[ $F = V$ ] then
7:       replace ‘[not] holdsAt( $F' = V', T$ )’ with ‘[not] holdsAtCyclic( $F' = V', T$ )’ in  $r$ 
8: return  $\mathcal{E}$ 

```

387 with the fluent dependency graph in Figure 1b, FVPs $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$ and
 388 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ have level 3 because the level of vertex $v_{interaction(P_1, P_2)}$ in
 389 $G_{\mathcal{E}_2}^{cdf}$ is 3. In the case of event description \mathcal{E}_3 , the vertex of the contracted fluent dependency
 390 graph corresponding to fluents $movement(P_1, P_2)$ and $interaction(P_1, P_2)$ has level 2 (see
 391 Figure 1d). Thus, FVPs $interaction(P_1, P_2) = greeting$, $movement(P_1, P_2) = gathering$,
 392 $interaction(P_1, P_2) = talking$ and $movement(P_1, P_2) = abrupt_gestures$ have level 2.

393 We can devise a local stratification of an event description by following bottom-up the
 394 levels of FVPs, as specified in Definition 14. For each level with cyclic dependencies, we
 395 introduce an additional stratum per time-point, following an ascending temporal order.

396 \blacktriangleright **Proposition 15** (Semantics of $RTEC_{\mathcal{F}}$). *An event description is a locally stratified logic*
 397 *program.* \blacklozenge

398 According to Proposition 15, $RTEC_{\mathcal{F}}$ supports every event description \mathcal{E} that follows
 399 Definition 1. If the dependency graph of \mathcal{E} contains FVPs with the same fluent whose vertices
 400 are in different levels of the graph, then these FVPs are assigned the same level, following
 401 the definition of FVP level in $RTEC_{\mathcal{F}}$ (see Definition 14), avoiding the issues described in
 402 Section 3.

403 4.2 Compiler

404 We developed a compiler that assigns a level to each FVP of an input event description
 405 \mathcal{E} and marks the holdsAt body conditions of the rules in \mathcal{E} that must be evaluated with
 406 incremental caching, in order to guarantee correct reasoning. The compilation is performed
 407 before the commencement of run-time reasoning, in a process transparent to the event
 408 description developer. Algorithm 1 outlines the compilation steps. First, we derive the
 409 levels of FVPs by following Definitions 13 and 14. We construct the contracted fluent
 410 dependency graph $G_{\mathcal{E}}^{cdf}$ of \mathcal{E} (line 1 of Algorithm 1). Then, we assign a level to each FVP
 411 in \mathcal{E} based on the level of the corresponding vertex of $G_{\mathcal{E}}^{cdf}$ (line 2). In order to identify
 412 the holdsAt conditions that need to be evaluated with incremental caching, the compiler
 413 works as follows. For each holdsAt($F' = V', T$) or ‘not holdsAt($F' = V', T$)’ condition in the
 414 body of a rule in \mathcal{E} , the compiler checks whether the level of FVP $F' = V'$ is equal to the
 415 level of the FVP in the head of the rule (lines 3–6). If this is the case, then we translate
 416 condition holdsAt($F' = V', T$) (resp. ‘not holdsAt($F' = V', T$)’) into holdsAtCyclic($F' = V', T$)
 417 (resp. ‘not holdsAtCyclic($F' = V', T$)’) (line 7). At run-time, $RTEC_{\mathcal{F}}$ evaluates the conditions
 418 with holdsAtCyclic using incremental caching (recall the second case presented in Section 2.2)
 419 and the conditions with holdsAt using the interval retrieval operation (see the first case of
 420 Section 2.2). A further discussion on run-time reasoning is presented in the section that
 421 follows.

422 We tested the compiler of $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ on event descriptions from various CER applications,
 423 including human activity recognition [2], city transport management [3] and maritime
 424 situational awareness [29, 30]. Moreover, we have used our compiler in applications that
 425 involve the monitoring of the normative positions of agents in multi-agent systems, such as
 426 e-commerce [35] and voting protocols [31]. In all cases, the compilation time amounted to a
 427 few milliseconds, and thus we do not show these times here. The compiler is available with
 428 the code of $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ ¹.

429 4.3 Reasoning & Complexity

430 $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ follows RTEC_{\circ} and processes FVPs in ascending FVP level order. When processing
 431 a rule that includes a $\text{holdsAtCyclic}(F' = V', T)$ condition, $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ computes the changes in
 432 the value of F' between T_{leq} and T , where T_{leq} is the last time-point before T where the
 433 truth value of $\text{holdsAt}(F' = V', T_{\text{leq}})$ has been evaluated and cached. In the worst-case, the
 434 cost of this process is $\mathcal{O}(\omega k)$, where ω is the size of the window and k is the cost of computing
 435 whether an FVP is initiated or terminated at a given time-point (see [3] for an estimation
 436 of k). This is the same incremental caching technique as the one used in RTEC_{\circ} , thus
 437 yielding the same cost [26]. In the case of a $\text{holdsAt}(F' = V', T)$ condition, $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ retrieves
 438 the maximal intervals of $F' = V'$ from its cache and checks whether T belongs to one of
 439 the retrieved intervals. Since the cached intervals are temporally sorted, this is achieved
 440 with a binary search, while the number of cached intervals of $F' = V'$ is bounded by ω .
 441 Therefore, the cost of an interval retrieval operation in $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is $\mathcal{O}(\log(\omega))$, which is the
 442 same as the cost of this operation in RTEC_{\circ} . As a result, $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ yields the same worst-case
 443 time complexity as RTEC_{\circ} , while supporting a wider range of temporal specifications. By
 444 following Definition 14 for FVP level, RTEC_{\circ} reasons with incremental caching only when it
 445 is necessary, i.e., only when the required intervals may not be present in the cache.

446 5 Summary and Future Work

447 We proposed $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$, an extension of RTEC_{\circ} , which detects composite activities based on
 448 their Event Calculus definitions, in order to support every possible set of such definitions. We
 449 described the syntax and semantics of $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$, demonstrating that activity specifications in
 450 $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ are locally stratified logic programs. Afterwards, we proposed a compiler for $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$,
 451 identifying the conditions of activity definitions that may be evaluated with an efficient cache
 452 operation, without sacrificing correctness, with the goal of improving reasoning efficiency at
 453 run-time. We outlined the worst-case time complexity of $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$, showing that it yields the
 454 same cost as RTEC_{\circ} . As a result, $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ supports a wider range of temporal specifications
 455 than RTEC_{\circ} , while maintaining its high reasoning efficiency. The code of $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is publicly
 456 available¹.

457 In the future, we aim to compare $\text{RTEC}_{\mathcal{F}}$ with automata-based activity recognition
 458 frameworks, such as [10, 40].

459 — References —

- 460 1 Elias Alevizos, Anastasios Skarlatidis, Alexander Artikis, and Georgios Paliouras. Probabilistic
 461 complex event recognition: A survey. *Commun. ACM*, 50(5):71:1–71:31, 2017.
- 462 2 Alexander Artikis, Marek J. Sergot, and Georgios Paliouras. A logic programming approach
 463 to activity recognition. In *EIMM Workshop in MM*, pages 3–8, 2010.
- 464 3 Alexander Artikis, Marek J. Sergot, and Georgios Paliouras. An event calculus for event
 465 recognition. *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.*, 27(4):895–908, 2015.

- 466 4 Hamid R. Bazoobandi, Harald Beck, and Jacopo Urbani. Expressive stream reasoning with
467 laser. In *ISWC*, volume 10587, pages 87–103, 2017.
- 468 5 Harald Beck, Minh Dao-Tran, and Thomas Eiter. LARS: A logic-based framework for analytic
469 reasoning over streams. *Artif. Intell.*, 261:16–70, 2018.
- 470 6 Harald Beck, Thomas Eiter, and Christian Folie. Ticker: A system for incremental asp-based
471 stream reasoning. *Theory Pract. Log. Program.*, 17(5-6):744–763, 2017.
- 472 7 Stefano Bragaglia, Federico Chesani, Paola Mello, Marco Montali, and Paolo Torroni. Reactive
473 event calculus for monitoring global computing applications. In *Logic Programs, Norms and
474 Action - Essays in Honor of Marek J. Sergot on the Occasion of His 60th Birthday*, volume
475 7360, pages 123–146, 2012.
- 476 8 Sebastian Brandt, Elem Güzel Kalayci, Vladislav Ryzhikov, Guohui Xiao, and Michael
477 Zakharyashev. Querying log data with metric temporal logic. *J. Artif. Intell. Res.*, 62:829–
478 877, 2018.
- 479 9 Stefano Bromuri, Visara Urovi, and Kostas Stathis. icampus: A connected campus in the
480 ambient event calculus. *Int. J. Ambient Comput. Intell.*, 2(1):59–65, 2010.
- 481 10 Marco Bucchi, Alejandro Grez, Andrés Quintana, Cristian Riveros, and Stijn Vansummeren.
482 CORE: a complex event recognition engine. *Proc. VLDB Endow.*, 15(9):1951–1964, 2022.
- 483 11 Francesco Calimeri, Marco Manna, Elena Mastria, Maria Concetta Morelli, Simona Perri, and
484 Jessica Zangari. I-dlv-sr: A stream reasoning system based on I-DLV. *Theory Pract. Log.
485 Program.*, 21(5):610–628, 2021.
- 486 12 Iliano Cervesato and Angelo Montanari. A calculus of macro-events: Progress report. In
487 *TIME*, pages 47–58, 2000.
- 488 13 Hervé Chaudet. Extending the event calculus for tracking epidemic spread. *Artif. Intell.
489 Medicine*, 38(2):137–156, 2006.
- 490 14 L. Chittaro and A. Montanari. Efficient temporal reasoning in the cached event calculus.
491 *Comput. Intell.*, 12(3):359–382, 1996.
- 492 15 Keith L. Clark. Negation as failure. In *Logic and Data Bases*, pages 293–322. Plenum Press,
493 1977.
- 494 16 Gianpaolo Cugola and Alessandro Margara. Processing flows of information: From data stream
495 to complex event processing. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 44(3), 2012.
- 496 17 C. Dousson and P. Le Maigat. Chronicle recognition improvement using temporal focusing
497 and hierarchisation. In *IJCAI*, pages 324–329, 2007.
- 498 18 Thomas Eiter, Paul Ogris, and Konstantin Schekotihin. A distributed approach to LARS
499 stream reasoning (system paper). *Theory Pract. Log. Program.*, 19(5-6):974–989, 2019.
- 500 19 Nicola Falcionelli, Paolo Sernani, Albert Brugués de la Torre, Dagmawi Neway Mekuria,
501 Davide Calvaresi, Michael Schumacher, Aldo Franco Dragoni, and Stefano Bromuri. Indexing
502 the event calculus: Towards practical human-readable personal health systems. *Artif. Intell.
503 Medicine*, 96:154–166, 2019.
- 504 20 Nikos Giatrakos, Elias Alevizos, Alexander Artikis, Antonios Deligiannakis, and Minos N.
505 Garofalakis. Complex event recognition in the big data era: a survey. *VLDB J.*, 29(1):313–352,
506 2020.
- 507 21 Alejandro Grez, Cristian Riveros, Martín Ugarte, and Stijn Vansummeren. A formal framework
508 for complex event recognition. *ACM Trans. Database Syst.*, 46(4):16:1–16:49, 2021.
- 509 22 Özgür Kafali, Alfonso E. Romero, and Kostas Stathis. Agent-oriented activity recognition in
510 the event calculus: An application for diabetic patients. *Comput. Intell.*, 33(4):899–925, 2017.
- 511 23 Nikos Katzouris, Georgios Paliouras, and Alexander Artikis. Online learning probabilistic event
512 calculus theories in answer set programming. *Theory Pract. Log. Program.*, 23(2):362–386,
513 2023.
- 514 24 Robert A. Kowalski and Marek J. Sergot. A logic-based calculus of events. *New Gener.
515 Comput.*, 4(1):67–95, 1986.
- 516 25 Periklis Mantenoglou, Dimitrios Kelesis, and Alexander Artikis. Complex event recognition
517 with allen relations. In *KR*, pages 502–511, 2023.

- 518 26 Periklis Mantenoglou, Manolis Pitsikalis, and Alexander Artikis. Stream reasoning with cycles.
519 In *KR*, pages 544–553, 2022.
- 520 27 Adrian Paschke. Eca-ruleml: An approach combining ECA rules with temporal interval-based
521 KR event/action logics and transactional update logics. *CoRR*, abs/cs/0610167, 2006.
- 522 28 Adrian Paschke and Martin Bichler. Knowledge representation concepts for automated SLA
523 management. *Decis. Support Syst.*, 46(1):187–205, 2008.
- 524 29 Kostas Patroumpas, Alexander Artikis, Nikos Katzouris, Marios Vodas, Yannis Theodoridis,
525 and Nikos Pelekis. Event recognition for maritime surveillance. In *EDBT*, pages 629–640,
526 2015.
- 527 30 Manolis Pitsikalis, Alexander Artikis, Richard Dreo, Cyril Ray, Elena Camossi, and Anne-
528 Laure Joussemme. Composite event recognition for maritime monitoring. In *DEBS*, pages
529 163–174, 2019.
- 530 31 J. Pitt, L. Kamara, M. Sergot, and A. Artikis. Voting in multi-agent systems. *Comput. J.*,
531 49(2):156–170, 2006.
- 532 32 Olga Poppe, Chuan Lei, Elke A. Rundensteiner, and David Maier. Event trend aggregation
533 under rich event matching semantics. In *SIGMOD*, pages 555–572, 2019.
- 534 33 Teodor C. Przymusiński. On the declarative semantics of deductive databases and logic
535 programs. In *Foundations of Deductive Databases and Logic Programming*, pages 193–216.
536 Morgan Kaufmann, 1988.
- 537 34 Nausheen Saba Shahid, Dan O’Keeffe, and Kostas Stathis. A knowledge representation
538 framework for evolutionary simulations with cognitive agents. In *ICTAI*, pages 361–368. IEEE,
539 2023.
- 540 35 M. Sirbu. Credits and debits on the Internet. *IEEE Spectrum*, 34(2):23–29, 1997.
- 541 36 Efthimis Tsilonis, Alexander Artikis, and Georgios Paliouras. Incremental event calculus for
542 run-time reasoning. *J. Artif. Intell. Res.*, 73:967–1023, 2022.
- 543 37 Przemyslaw Andrzej Walega, Mark Kaminski, and Bernardo Cuenca Grau. Reasoning over
544 streaming data in metric temporal datalog. In *AAAI*, pages 3092–3099, 2019.
- 545 38 Przemyslaw Andrzej Walega, Mark Kaminski, Dingmin Wang, and Bernardo Cuenca Grau.
546 Stream reasoning with datalogmtl. *J. Web Semant.*, 76:100776, 2023.
- 547 39 Bo Zhao, Han van der Aa, Thanh Tam Nguyen, Quoc Viet Hung Nguyen, and Matthias
548 Weidlich. EIRES: efficient integration of remote data in event stream processing. In *SIGMOD*,
549 pages 2128–2141, 2021.
- 550 40 Bartosz Zielinski. Explanatory denotational semantics for complex event patterns. *Formal*
551 *Aspects Comput.*, 35(4):23:1–23:37, 2023.